

Impact of Thyroid Dysfunction on Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients Attending at Outpatient Department

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Abstract

Background: Thyroid dysfunction (TD) is a common endocrine disorder that frequently coexists with chronic kidney disease (CKD), potentially exacerbating renal impairment. The interplay between thyroid hormones and kidney function is complex, with thyroid abnormalities often leading to alterations in glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). Despite growing evidence, the specific impact of thyroid dysfunction on eGFR in CKD patients remains underexplored, particularly in resource-limited settings. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of thyroid dysfunction on eGFR in CKD patients attending at Outpatient Department of Nephrology Community Based Medical College Bangladesh. **Methods:** A cross-sectional observational study was conducted involving 87 CKD patients selected through purposive sampling. Data on thyroid function tests (TFTs) and eGFR were collected. Thyroid dysfunction was categorized based on serum TSH and free thyroxine (FT4) levels, while eGFR was calculated using the CKD-EPI equation. Data analysis was performed using the SPSS version 23.0 program. **Results:** Thyroid dysfunction was present in 38% of CKD patients, with hypothyroidism being the most common (25%). Hypothyroid patients had significantly lower eGFR levels compared to euthyroid patients ($p < 0.01$). A strong inverse correlation was found between TSH and eGFR ($r = -0.62, p < 0.001$). Thyroid dysfunction was an independent predictor of reduced eGFR ($\hat{\alpha} = -0.48, p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Thyroid dysfunction, particularly hypothyroidism, is prevalent in CKD patients and significantly associated with reduced eGFR. Routine thyroid screening and early intervention may help preserve renal function. Further studies are needed to explore causal relationships and long-term outcomes in CKD populations with thyroid dysfunction.

Keywords: Thyroid dysfunction, Chronic kidney disease, Estimated glomerular filtration rate, Hypothyroidism, Renal function

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global public health concern, affecting approximately 10 percent of the world's population, with a rising prevalence in low- and middle-

income countries¹. CKD is characterized by a gradual loss of kidney function, often leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality^{2,3}. The progression of CKD is influenced by

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various comorbidities, including diabetes, hypertension, and endocrine disorders such as thyroid dysfunction (TD)⁴. Thyroid hormones play a critical role in regulating metabolism, cardiovascular function, and renal hemodynamics, making thyroid dysfunction a potential modifier of kidney function⁵. Thyroid dysfunction, encompassing both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism, is frequently observed in CKD patients, with reported prevalence rates ranging from 10 percent to 50 percent^{6,7}. Hypothyroidism, in particular, is more common in CKD populations and has been associated with reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR) due to decreased cardiac output, renal plasma flow, and sodium reabsorption^{8,9}. Conversely, hyperthyroidism can lead to increased GFR but may also exacerbate proteinuria and renal injury⁴. The relationship between thyroid dysfunction and CKD is bidirectional, as kidney disease can also alter thyroid hormone metabolism, leading to a condition known as “non-thyroidal illness syndrome” or “euthyroid sick syndrome”¹⁰. Another study has primarily focused on Western populations, and data from South Asian countries are scarce¹¹. Despite the growing body of evidence highlighting the interplay between thyroid dysfunction and CKD, the specific impact of thyroid abnormalities on estimated GFR (eGFR) in CKD patients remains inadequately explored, particularly in resource-limited settings like Bangladesh. Understanding this relationship is crucial for optimizing the management of CKD patients, as early detection and treatment of thyroid dysfunction may help slow the progression of renal impairment⁶. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of thyroid dysfunction on eGFR in CKD patients attending the Outpatient Department of Nephrology Community Based Medical College Bangladesh. By assessing the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction and its correlation with eGFR, this study seeks to provide insights into the clinical significance of thyroid screening in CKD management. The findings may contribute to the development of integrated care strategies for CKD patients with comorbid thyroid dysfunction, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Methodology

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Outpatient Department of Nephrology Community Based Medical College Bangladesh, from January 2023 to December 2024. A purposive sampling technique was employed to enroll 87 CKD patients aged 18 years and above, diagnosed with CKD stages 1–5 based on the

kidney disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines. Patients with acute kidney injury, pregnancy, or a history of thyroidectomy were excluded. Data on demographic characteristics, medical history, and laboratory parameters, including serum creatinine, thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (FT4), and free triiodothyronine (FT3), were collected. Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was calculated using the CKD-EPI equation. Thyroid dysfunction was classified as hypothyroidism (TSH > 4.5 mIU/L with low FT4), hyperthyroidism (TSH < 0.4 mIU/L with high FT4), or subclinical dysfunction (abnormal TSH with normal FT4). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, Pearson’s correlation, and independent t-tests were used to assess the relationship between thyroid dysfunction and eGFR. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board, and informed consent was secured from all participants.

Results

The study population had a mean age of 52.4 years, with a slight male predominance (54%). Hypertension (75%) and diabetes (60%) were the most common comorbidities. A significant proportion of patients (43%) were in advanced CKD stages (4–5) (Table I). Thyroid dysfunction was present in 38% of CKD patients, with hypothyroidism being the most common (25%). Subclinical hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism were less prevalent (Table II). Patients with hypothyroidism had significantly lower eGFR levels compared to euthyroid patients ($p < 0.01$). Subclinical hypothyroidism also showed reduced eGFR, though to a lesser extent ($p < 0.05$) (Table III). A strong inverse correlation was observed between TSH levels and eGFR ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher TSH levels (hypothyroidism) were associated with lower eGFR (Table IV). Hypothyroid patients had significantly lower eGFR levels compared to euthyroid patients ($p < 0.01$), emphasizing the adverse impact of hypothyroidism on renal function (Table V). The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction increased with advancing CKD stages, reaching 45% in stages 4–5 ($p < 0.01$) (Table VI). Patients with thyroid dysfunction had a higher prevalence of diabetes (65%) compared to euthyroid patients (55%, $p < 0.05$) (Table VII). Hypertension was common in both groups but not significantly different. Thyroid dysfunction was the strongest independent predictor of reduced eGFR ($\hat{\alpha} = -0.48$, $p < 0.001$), followed by hypertension and diabetes (Table VIII).

Table-I

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Variable	Number	Percentage
Mean age (years)	52.4 ± 12.3	
Male	47	54%
Female	40	46%
Hypertension	65	75%
Diabetes	52	60%
CKD Stage 1–2	20	23%
CKD Stage 3	30	34%
CKD Stage 4–5	37	43%

Table-II

Prevalence of Thyroid Dysfunction among CKD Patients

Thyroid Status	Number	Percentage
Euthyroid	54	62%
Hypothyroidism	22	25%
SH	9	10%
Hyperthyroidism	2	3%

SH: Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Table-III

Comparison of eGFR Across Thyroid Function Statuses

Thyroid Status	Mean eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	p-value
Euthyroid	45.8 ± 12.4	-
Hypothyroidism	32.5 ± 10.2	<0.01*
SH	38.2 ± 11.5	<0.05
Hyperthyroidism	48.6 ± 13.1	>0.05

SH: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, *Statistically significant

Table-IV

Correlation Between TSH Levels and eGFR

Parameter	CC(r)	p-value
TSH vs. eGFR	-0.62	<0.001*

CC: Correlation Coefficient, *Statistically significant

Table-V

Subgroup Analysis of eGFR in Hypothyroid vs. Euthyroid Patients

Group	Mean eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	p-value
Hypothyroid	32.5 ± 10.2	<0.01*
Euthyroid	45.8 ± 12.4	>0.05

*Statistically significant, *Statistically significant

Table-VI

Association Between CKD Stages and Thyroid Dysfunction

CKD Stage	Thyroid Dysfunction (%)	p-value
Stage 1–2	22%	<0.05
Stage 3	30%	<0.05
Stage 4–5	45%	<0.01*

*Statistically significant

Table-VII

Prevalence of Comorbidities in Patients with Thyroid Dysfunction

Comorbidity	TD (%)	Euthyroid (%)	p-value
Hypertension	78%	72%	>0.05
Diabetes	65%	55%	<0.05*

TD: Thyroid Dysfunction, *Statistically significant

Table-VIII

Multivariate Analysis of Factors Influencing eGFR

Factor	β-coefficient	p-value
Thyroid Dysfunction	-0.48	<0.001*
Hypertension	-0.22	<0.05*
Diabetes	-0.18	<0.05*
Age	-0.12	>0.05

*Statistically significant

Discussion

This study highlights the significant association between thyroid dysfunction and reduced estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) in chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients, with a particular focus on the Bangladeshi population. The findings reveal that thyroid dysfunction is prevalent in 38% of CKD patients, with hypothyroidism being the most common abnormality (25%). This is

consistent with previous studies that have reported a high prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in CKD populations, ranging from 10% to 50%^{4,6}. The strong inverse correlation between TSH levels and eGFR ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.001$) underscores the detrimental impact of hypothyroidism on renal function, as evidenced by significantly lower eGFR levels in hypothyroid patients compared to euthyroid individuals ($p < 0.01$)^{8,9}. The study population had a mean age of 52.4 years, with a slight male predominance (54%). Hypertension (75%) and diabetes (60%) were the most common comorbidities, which aligns with global trends where these conditions are major contributors to CKD progression^{2,12}. A significant proportion of patients (43%) were in advanced CKD stages (4–5), and the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction increased with worsening CKD severity, reaching 45% in stages 4–5 ($p < 0.01$). This finding is consistent with the bidirectional relationship between thyroid dysfunction and CKD, where declining renal function exacerbates thyroid hormone abnormalities, and vice versa^{10,13}. Hypothyroid patients exhibited significantly lower eGFR levels compared to euthyroid patients ($p < 0.01$), emphasizing the adverse impact of hypothyroidism on renal function. This is likely due to reduced cardiac output, decreased renal plasma flow, and impaired sodium reabsorption associated with hypothyroidism^{4,5}. Subclinical hypothyroidism also showed reduced eGFR, though to a lesser extent ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that even mild thyroid dysfunction can negatively affect renal function. Patients with thyroid dysfunction had a higher prevalence of diabetes (65%) compared to euthyroid patients (55%, $p < 0.05$), highlighting the interplay between endocrine disorders and CKD. Hypertension, although common in both groups, did not show a significant difference, possibly due to its high prevalence in the general CKD population^{1,11}. Multivariate analysis identified thyroid dysfunction as the strongest independent predictor of reduced eGFR ($\beta = -0.48$, $p < 0.001$), followed by hypertension and diabetes. This underscores the importance of routine thyroid function screening in CKD patients to identify and manage thyroid dysfunction early, potentially slowing CKD progression^{6,13}. The findings of this study were consistent with previous research, which has demonstrated a high prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in CKD patients and its association with reduced eGFR^{15,16}. However, this study adds to the limited data from South Asian populations, particularly Bangladesh, where resource constraints often limit comprehensive screening and management of comorbidities in CKD patients.

Conclusion

Thyroid dysfunction, particularly hypothyroidism, is prevalent in CKD patients and is strongly associated with reduced eGFR. Routine screening for thyroid dysfunction in CKD patients is essential for early detection and management, which may help preserve renal function and improve patient outcomes. Further large-scale studies are recommended to explore the causal relationships and long-term outcomes of thyroid dysfunction in CKD populations.

Limitations

This study has a small sample size ($n = 87$) and was cross-sectional design, limiting causal inferences. The single-center study may affect generalizability. Additionally, the lack of longitudinal data prevents assessment of long-term outcomes.

Recommendations

Routine screening for thyroid dysfunction should be integrated into the management of CKD patients, particularly in advanced stages. Early detection and treatment of thyroid abnormalities may help preserve renal function and improve outcomes. Further research is needed to establish causal relationships and explore the benefits of thyroid hormone replacement therapy in CKD populations.

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